

FIBER REINFORCED PIEZOELECTRIC COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, multifunctional carbon fiber composites are fabricated using two different approaches for integrating piezoelectric properties into the composite. The first approach integrates zinc oxide (ZnO) nanorod coated Kevlar fibers into the carbon fiber composite structure while the second approach utilizes barium titanate (BTO) coated carbon fibers. These approaches create composites that exhibit piezoelectric properties while maintaining their mechanical integrity for use in load bearing applications. Low-cost, hydrothermal processes are used to synthesize both vertically aligned arrays of ZnO nanorods and BTO nanowire textured films on the Kevlar fiber's and carbon fiber's surfaces, respectively. These growth procedures allow for the growth on woven fabrics thus enabling simplified composite integration and fabrication. These fabrics are placed between carbon fiber fabrics and molded via a vacuum-assisted resin transfer molding technique to form the bulk composite structure. The piezoelectric properties of ZnO and BTO allow the composites to convert mechanical strain induced from ambient vibrations to electrical energy via the direct piezoelectric effect. To characterize the power harvesting potential of these composites, they are fashioned into cantilevered sections and subjected to accelerations via a permanent magnet shaker. Measuring the voltage output across various resistance loads as a function of base acceleration reveals the power output. This research demonstrates novel approaches to fabricate multifunctional composite systems with piezoelectric and load-bearing properties.

1 INTRODUCTION

Piezoelectric 1-D nanostructures have attracted significant research interests as a result of the variety of applications that benefit from nano-scale structures capable of converting electrical energy to mechanical energy and vice versa. Additionally, the development of numerous routes to synthesis piezoelectric nanostructures of various dimensions and compositions has added research interests in a wide range of fields. Specifically, these nanostructures have seen integration in sensors, such as in electrochemical,[1, 2] gas,[3-5], and mechanical vibration sensing[6] as a result of the high compliance and surface area-to-volume ratio inherent in 1-D nanostructures. The power harvesting field has also implemented these nanostructured piezoelectrics to generate power from ambient vibrations for use in low-power systems thus enabling wireless, self-powered electronic systems that negate the need for large volumes of power storage.[7] The drawback to these applications have been that they provide only one functionality, i.e. power generating or sensing. To further progress this field of nanostructured

piezoelectrics and increase the efficiency and performance of existing structures, the concept of multifunctionality has been developed in which multiple performance objectives are met while minimizing the complexity of the overall system.

Multifunctionality can be achieved in composites through the addition of actuation, [8-12] sensing,[13-15] structural health monitoring,[16] power generation and storage,[17-19] vibration damping,[20-22] and ballistic protection functionalities.[23] Past research efforts have demonstrated one route to creating these multifunctional composites through the development of piezoelectric fiber reinforced composites. For example, fibers composed of piezoelectric materials, such as lead zirconate titanate, have been synthesized and integrated into composites to serve as the active phase while also offering mechanical support. However, the mechanical strength of these piezoelectric fiber composites were significantly reduced due to the large diameter and brittleness of the fibers.[9, 10] An active phase was integrated into a reinforcing fiber using a barium titanate (BTO) shell around a silicon carbide core by Lin *et al.*, but the large diameter fiber core was still not suitable for load bearing composite implementation.[24, 25] The challenge with active phase integration into composites is creating a composite that has sufficient mechanical strength to serve in load bearing applications.

In this research, the piezoelectric behavior of zinc oxide (ZnO) and the ferroelectric property of BTO are combined with the high performance mechanical properties of carbon fiber. Prior research efforts have demonstrated the deposition of ZnO nanowires (NWs) on Kevlar fibers and a BTO textured film on carbon fibers.[26, 27] Utilizing these growth procedures, Kevlar woven fabrics coated with ZnO NWs and carbon fiber woven fabrics coated with a textured BTO film are placed between carbon fiber fabric plies and resin-molded into composite structures. Coupling the active properties of these piezoelectric and ferroelectric materials with the strength of carbon fibers creates an efficient and high performance multifunctional composite capable of providing load bearing structural support.

2 EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

2.1 Zinc Oxide Synthesis

ZnO NWs were grown on aramid fabrics via a low temperature hydrothermal process after proper surface modification and nanoparticle deposition procedures. Aramid fabrics (Kevlar KM2 Style 706 scoured, CS-800, JPS composite) were cleaned by submerging them in boiling acetone and ethanol sequentially to remove any residual organics on the surface. These clean fiber surfaces were then chemically modified to increase the adhesion between the fiber surface and the ZnO NWs. The surface modification process consisted of soaking in a 10 wt% aqueous sodium hydroxide (NaOH, EMD Millipore, 99.5%) solution for 20 minutes then performing an ion exchange process in 35 wt% aqueous hydrochloric acid (HCl, Fisher) as described in further detail elsewhere.[28] After cleaning and surface modification, the ZnO NWs were synthesized through a two-step process of nanoparticle deposition and hydrothermal reaction. Nanoparticle deposition was achieved by dipping the fabrics in a colloidal suspension of ZnO nanoparticles according to the process described by Hu *et al.*[29] This colloidal suspension consisted of 1 mmol of zinc acetate dehydrate (Alfa Aesar, 99.5%) dissolved in 80 mL of ethanol and 2 mmol of NaOH dissolved in 100 mL of ethanol. 40 mL of the zinc acetate solution was added to 320 mL of ethanol and the 40 mL of the NaOH solution was added to 100 mL of ethanol. These solutions were heated separately to 65 °C before being mixed together under vigorous stirring. The combined solution was kept at 65 °C for 45 minutes. The aramid fabrics were dipped in this solution and annealed at 150 °C for 10 minutes. This dip-coating and annealing process was repeated three times to obtain a sufficient nanoparticle seed layer for the ZnO nucleation during hydrothermal synthesis.

A hydrothermal growth solution was prepared by dissolving 48 mM $\text{Zn}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Sigma-Aldrich, $\geq 99.0\%$), 24 mM hexamethylenetetramine (Sigma-Aldrich, $\geq 99.0\%$), 7.7 mM polyethylenimine (Sigma-Aldrich, average Mw ~ 800) and 2 mM of $\text{Cd}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Fisher Scientific, $\geq 98.0\%$) in deionized water. After complete dissolution, 11.5 mL of ammonia solution (28 wt% in water, Ricca, 28.0–30.0 wt %) was added in order to arrive at a final NH_4OH concentration of 0.49 M. The

fabrics and this growth solution were added to a closed container and heated at 86 °C for 2.5 hours to grow the arrays of ZnO NWs.[30]

2.2 Barium Titanate Synthesis

A BTO textured film was grown on carbon fiber fabrics (FG-CARB5750 supplied by U.S. Composites, Inc) via a two-step hydrothermal reaction with a pre-growth nanoparticle seeding step. The carbon fiber fabrics were seeded with TiO₂ nanoparticles through a dip-coating process using a titanium sol-gel made from a solution of concentrated HCl, isopropanol, and titanium isopropoxide. The fabrics were dipped in the solution then heat treated at 120 °C for 1 hour to create a TiO₂ nanoparticle seed layer to assist in the nucleation of TiO₂ NWs during the hydrothermal reaction. A hydrothermal growth solution was prepared with a 1:2 volumetric ratio of titanium tetrachloride (Alfa Aesar, 99.0%) and titanium isopropoxide (Alfa Aesar, VERTEC TIPT, 97+%) in a 1:1 volumetric ratio of concentrated HCl (Fisher, 35%) and deionized water.[27] This solution and the fabric were combined in a sealed Teflon container in a steel enclosure and heated to 180 °C for 3 hours. This process resulted in the growth of a dense array of TiO₂ NWs. These NWs were then converted to BTO using a second hydrothermal reaction that diffused Ba²⁺ ions into the TiO₂ crystal structure. The mechanisms of this reaction are described in further details elsewhere.[31-35] This reaction solution contained 1.2 M barium chloride (Fisher, 99.5%) and 0.75M NaOH (EMD Millipore, 99.5%) dissolved in deionized water. The TiO₂ coated fabrics and this solution were placed in a sealed Teflon container in a steel enclosure and heated to 225 °C for 24 hours. The resulting material was a textured BTO film on the surface of the carbon fibers.

2.3 Composite Fabrication

The ZnO coated Kevlar fabric and the BTO coated carbon fiber fabric were used to make different composites for energy harvesting. In both cases, two layers of carbon fiber fabric were placed under the nanomaterial-coated fabrics with one layer of carbon fabric placed on top of the nanomaterial-coated fabrics. The bare carbon fiber fabrics served as the top and bottom electrodes for contacting the ZnO and BTO. In the case of the BTO composite, an additional layer material was added. An aluminum foil was placed on top of the BTO fabric before adding the one top layer of carbon fiber. This provided a means to electrode the BTO without shorting. These stacked fabrics were made into a composite by infiltrating with epoxy using a conventional vacuum-assisted resin transfer molding (VARTM) technique. The epoxy matrix used here consisted of a 100:35 weight ratio of Epon 862 and Epikure 3230. The epoxy was able to completely infiltrate the fabrics within a few minutes. Upon complete infiltration, the composite was left under vacuum and allowed to cure at room temperature for 10 hours. The composites were then released from the vacuum and heat treated at 80 °C for two hours followed by heating at 125 °C for three hours. Upon cooling to room temperature, the composites were machined into the desired geometries. The ZnO composite was sectioned into a beam measuring 30 mm by 10 mm, while the BTO composite was sectioned in a beam with dimensions of 20 mm by 10 mm. To measure the voltage and current outputs of these devices, electrodes were connected to the top and bottom carbon fiber fabrics by scratching off the top layer of epoxy and attaching 33 gage wires with silver paint. Due to the ferroelectric nature of BTO, an additional poling procedure is performed before power harvesting measurements. This was achieved via a conventional poling technique in which the two wire leads from the composite were connected to a 5V DC power supply and held at this voltage for a minimum of 12 hours.

2.4 Power Harvesting

The beams were mounted in a cantilever configuration in which one end was fixed and the other was free to move. The fixed end was placed on a permanent magnet shaker with a tip mass on the free end. A base acceleration was provided to the fixed end and was measured with a commercial shear accelerometer (PCB 352C22). The voltage output of the sample was measured using a high impedance (1T Ω) voltage follower, which utilizes a Linear Technologies Op Amp (LTC6240CS8CMOS). Power

measurements were made by inserting load resistances into the circuit and measuring the voltage output. Current measurements were collected using a high speed electrometer (Keithley 6514). NI SignalExpress Software in conjunction with a DAQ board (NI USB 4431) were used to generate the excitation waveforms and acquire output voltage and currents.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Morphology and Crystal Structure

The morphologies of the ZnO NWs on Kevlar fabric and the BTO textured films on carbon fiber were investigated using a scanning electron microscope (SEM, TESCAN VEGA3 LM). As shown in Fig. 1, the fabrics have full coverage by the nanomaterials following the growth procedures. Fig. 1 (a) and (b) clearly show uniform growth of ZnO NWs while Fig. 1 (c) and (d) show the uniform growth of BTO films.

Figure 1: (a) The ZnO on Kevlar shows complete fiber coverage with (b) individual NWs observed. (c) The BTO on carbon fiber also shows complete coverage over the fabric and are (d) uniform films.

The crystal structure was investigated with X-ray diffraction (XRD, PANalytical X'Pert Powder). The XRD patterns (Fig. 2) for the ZnO on Kevlar showed characteristic peaks matching the JCPDS card no. 79-2205 for ZnO with low degree, broad peaks matching that of Kevlar. The XRD patterns for the growth and conversion on carbon fiber fabric showed the characteristic peaks for rutile TiO₂ (JCPDS card no. 75-1754) after the first growth and characteristic peaks of BTO (JCPDS card no. 05-0626) after

the conversion reaction with some unconverted TiO₂ still present in the film. These patterns confirm the growth of ZnO and the conversion of most of the TiO₂ to BTO.

Figure 2: The XRD patterns indicate the presence of ZnO on the Kevlar fabric. On the carbon fiber fabric, the characteristic peaks indicate that the rutile TiO₂ was converted to BTO with some remnant TiO₂ present

3.2 Power Harvesting

The power harvesting capabilities of these fabricated multifunctional composites were investigated through vibration testing. The mechanical vibrations at the base of the cantilever caused the free end of the beam to flex thus transferring stress to the ZnO and BTO layers inside the composite. This stress causes a voltage and current output. The cantilevers were excited with a white Gaussian noise signal to perform a frequency response function (FRF) characterization. This allows the resonant frequency of the system to be measured. A sine wave input at the resonant frequency gives the maximum voltage output. Measuring this voltage output across load resistors placed in the circuit reveal the power output of the beam according to Equation 1

$$P_L = I_{L(RMS)}^2 R_L = \left(\frac{V_{RMS}}{Z_s + R_L} \right)^2 R_L = \frac{V_L^2(RMS)}{R_L} \quad (1)$$

For the ZnO coated Kevlar fabric composite, a tip mass of 45 grams was added to increase the stress on the beam and to lower the resonant frequency. As shown in the FRF plots in Fig. 3, a resonant frequency was observed at 212 Hz as indicated by an increase in the magnitude response in Fig. 3 (a) and a 180 ° phase change in Fig 3 (b). Using a sine wave excitation at 212 Hz, a peak-to-peak voltage (V_{pp}) of 50 mV was measured as illustrated in Fig 3 (c).

Figure 3: The FRF (a) magnitude and (b) phase plots indicate a resonant frequency at 212 Hz for the ZnO coated Kevlar composite. (c) 212 Hz sine wave base acceleration produced a peak-to-peak voltage of 50mV.

The same white Gaussian noise excitation was used on the BTO coated carbon fiber composite. With a tip mass of 20 g, a resonant frequency of 47 Hz was observed (Fig. 4 a)). A V_{pp} of 20mV and V_{RMS} of 5.15 mV was produced at this frequency under sine wave excitation with a root-mean-square acceleration of 1.01g as illustrated in Fig. 4 (b). At the same frequency and similar base acceleration, the composite generated a peak-to-peak current (I_{pp}) of 160 nA (Fig. 4(c)). While keeping the acceleration and frequency constant, resistors were added to the circuit in order to calculate the power dissipation according to Eq. 1. Fig. 5 (a) shows the effect the additional resistance had on the voltage FRF near the resonant frequency. It can be seen that the open circuit has the highest voltage response, and this response decreases as the resistance is decreased. The peak power density plot (Fig. 5 (b)) shows a maximum power density of 217 pW/cc at a resistance of 250 k Ω .

Figure 4: (a) The voltage FRF indicated a resonance at 47 Hz. Using a 47 Hz sine wave the (a) voltage output and (b) current output had peak-to-peak values of approximately 20 mV and 160 nA, respectively.

Figure 5: (a) The voltage response FRF showed a decreasing output with decreasing resistance. (b) The peak power density is approximately 217 pW/cc at an optimum resistance of 250 kΩ

4 CONCLUSIONS

Nanostructured piezoelectric and ferroelectric materials were deposited on strong core fibers in a woven fabric configuration. These fabrics were integrated into carbon fiber composites via a conventional VARTM technique. The resulting composites were fashioned into smaller beams and fixed at one end to create a cantilever device setup. These beams were subjected to mechanical vibrations via a permanent magnet shaker and natural frequencies of 212 Hz and 47 Hz were measured for the ZnO on Kevlar fiber and BTO on carbon fiber composites, respectively. The V_{pp} output of the ZnO composite at resonance was 50 mV while the BTO composite saw a V_{pp} of 20 mV with a I_{pp} of 160 nA. For the BTO composite, a peak power density was calculated to be 217 pW/cc at an optimum resistance of 250 k Ω and a root-mean-square acceleration of approximately 1g. Therefore, these two different samples have demonstrated the ability to integrate nanostructured piezoelectrics into a bulk carbon fiber composite thus providing a strong composite that is capable of functioning as a power generation device.

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REFERENCES

- [1] A.K. Wanekaya, W. Chen, N.V. Myung and A. Mulchandani, Nanowire- based electrochemical biosensors, *Electroanalysis*, **18**, 2006, pp. 533-550 (doi: 10.1002/elan.200503449).
- [2] U. Yogeswaran and S. Chen, A review on the electrochemical sensors and biosensors composed of nanowires as sensing material, *Sensors*, **8**, 2008, pp. 290-313.
- [3] X. Chen, C.K. Wong, C.A. Yuan and G. Zhang, Nanowire-based gas sensors, *Sensors Actuators B: Chem.*, **177**, 2013, pp. 178-195 (doi: 10.1016/j.snb.2012.10.134).
- [4] N. Hongsoth, C. Viriyaworasakul, P. Mangkorntong, N. Mangkorntong and S. Choopun, Ethanol sensor based on ZnO and Au-doped ZnO nanowires, *Ceram.Int.*, **34**, 2008, pp. 823-826 (doi: 10.1016/j.ceramint.2007.09.099).
- [5] C.S. Rout, S. Hari Krishna, S. Vivekchand, A. Govindaraj and C. Rao, Hydrogen and ethanol sensors based on ZnO nanorods, nanowires and nanotubes, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, **418**, 2006, pp. 586-590 (doi: 10.1016/j.cplett.2005.11.040).
- [6] A. Koka and H.A. Sodano, High-sensitivity accelerometer composed of ultra-long vertically aligned barium titanate nanowire arrays, *Nat. Commun.*, **4**, 2013 (doi: 10.1038/ncomms3682).
- [7] A. Koka, Z. Zhou and H.A. Sodano, Vertically aligned BaTiO₃ nanowire arrays for energy harvesting, *Energy Environ. Sci.*, **7**, 2014, pp. 288-296 (doi: 10.1039/C3EE42540A).
- [8] K. Li, Y. Wang, H. Wang, M. Zhu and H. Yan, Hydrothermal synthesis and photocatalytic properties of layered La₂Ti₂O₇ nanosheets, *Nanotechnology*, **17**, 2006, pp. 4863 (doi: 10.1088/0957-4484/17/19/014).
- [9] N. Hagood and A. Bent, Development of piezoelectric fiber composites for structural actuation, *AIAA Paper*, 1993, pp. 3625-3638 (doi: 10.2514/6.1993-1717).
- [10] A.A. Bent, N.W. Hagood and J.P. Rodgers, Anisotropic actuation with piezoelectric fiber composites, *J. Intell. Mater. Syst. Struct.*, **6**, 1995, pp. 338-349 (doi: 10.1177/1045389X9500600305).
- [11] J.M. Haberl, A. Sánchez- Ferrer, A.M. Mihut, H. Dietsch, A.M. Hirt and R. Mezzenga, Light-controlled actuation, transduction, and modulation of magnetic strength in polymer nanocomposites, *Adv. Funct. Mater.*, **24**, 2014, pp. 3179-3186 (doi: 10.1002/adfm.201304218).
- [12] G.A. Sotiriou, C.O. Blattmann and S.E. Pratsinis, Flexible, multifunctional, magnetically actuated nanocomposite films, *Adv. Funct. Mater.*, **23**, 2013, pp. 34-41 (doi: 10.1002/adfm.201201371).

- [13] H.A. Sodano, G. Park and D.J. Inman, An investigation into the performance of macro-fiber composites for sensing and structural vibration applications, *Mechanical Systems and Signal Processing*, **18**, 2004, pp. 683-697 (doi: 10.1016/S0888-3270(03)00081-5).
- [14] J. Tressler, S. Alkoy, A. Dogan and R. Newnham, Functional composites for sensors, actuators and transducers, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **30**, 1999, pp. 477-482 (doi: 10.1016/S1359-835X(98)00137-7).
- [15] S. Gao, R. Zhuang, J. Zhang, J. Liu and E. Mäder, Glass fibers with carbon nanotube networks as multifunctional sensors, *Adv. Funct. Mater.*, **20**, 2010, pp. 1885-1893 (doi: 10.1002/adfm.201000283).
- [16] C. Li and T. Chou, Modeling of damage sensing in fiber composites using carbon nanotube networks, *Composites Sci. Technol.*, **68**, 2008, pp. 3373-3379 (doi: 10.1016/j.compscitech.2008.09.025).
- [17] Y. Lin and H.A. Sodano, Concept and model of a piezoelectric structural fiber for multifunctional composites, *Composites Sci. Technol.*, **68**, 2008, pp. 1911-1918 (doi: 10.1016/j.compscitech.2007.12.017).
- [18] H.A. Sodano, D.J. Inman and G. Park, A review of power harvesting from vibration using piezoelectric materials, *Shock Vib. Dig.*, **36**, 2004, pp. 197-206 (doi: 10.1177/0583102404043275).
- [19] B. Tian, X. Zheng, T.J. Kempa, Y. Fang, N. Yu, G. Yu, J. Huang and C.M. Lieber, Coaxial silicon nanowires as solar cells and nanoelectronic power sources, *Nature*, **449**, 2007, pp. 885-889 (doi: 10.1038/nature06181).
- [20] M.H. Malakooti, H. Hwang and H.A. Sodano, Morphology-Controlled ZnO Nanowire Arrays for Tailored Hybrid Composites with High Damping, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces*, 2014 (doi: 10.1021/am506272c).
- [21] V.P. Veedu, A. Cao, X. Li, K. Ma, C. Soldano, S. Kar, P.M. Ajayan and M.N. Ghasemi-Nejhad, Multifunctional composites using reinforced laminae with carbon-nanotube forests, *Nature Mater.*, **5**, 2006, pp. 457-462 (doi: 10.1038/nmat1650).
- [22] S. Raja, G. Prathap and P. Sinha, Active vibration control of composite sandwich beams with piezoelectric extension-bending and shear actuators, *Smart Mater. Struct.*, **11**, 2002, pp. 63 (doi: 10.1088/0964-1726/11/1/307).
- [23] K.S. Vecchio, Synthetic multifunctional metallic-intermetallic laminate composites, *JOM*, **57**, 2005, pp. 25-31 (doi: 10.1007/s11837-005-0229-4).
- [24] Y. Lin and H.A. Sodano, Characterization of multifunctional structural capacitors for embedded energy storage, *J.Appl.Phys.*, **106**, 2009, pp. 114108-114108-5 (doi: 10.1063/1.3267482).
- [25] Y. Lin and H.A. Sodano, Electromechanical characterization of a active structural fiber lamina for multifunctional composites, *Compos. Sci. Technol.*, **69**, 2009, pp. 1825-1830 (doi: 10.1016/j.compscitech.2009.03.022).
- [26] H. Hwang, M.H. Malakooti, B.A. Patterson and H.A. Sodano, Increased inter yarn friction through ZnO nanowire arrays grown on aramid fabric, *Compos. Sci. Technol.*, **107**, 2015, pp. 75-81 (doi: 10.1016/j.compscitech.2014.12.001).
- [27] C. Bowland, Z. Zhou and H.A. Sodano, Multifunctional Barium Titanate Coated Carbon Fibers, *Adv. Funct. Mater.*, **24**, 2014, pp. 6303-6308 (doi: 10.1002/adfm.201401417).
- [28] G.J. Ehlert and H.A. Sodano, Zinc oxide nanowire interphase for enhanced interfacial strength in lightweight polymer fiber composites, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces*, **1**, 2009, pp. 1827-1833 (doi: 10.1021/am900376t).
- [29] Z. Hu, G. Oskam and P.C. Searson, Influence of solvent on the growth of ZnO nanoparticles, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.*, **263**, 2003, pp. 454-460 (doi: 10.1016/S0021-9797(03)00205-4).
- [30] M.H. Malakooti, H. Hwang and H.A. Sodano, Power generation from base excitation of a Kevlar composite beam with ZnO nanowires, *Proceedings of SPIE Smart Structures and*

Materials Nondestructive Evaluation and Health Monitoring, San Diego, California, March 8, 2015, pp.94320W-94320W-6.

- [31] W. Hertl, Kinetics of barium titanate synthesis, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.*, **71**, 1988, pp. 879-883 (doi: 10.1111/j.1151-2916.1988.tb07540.x).
- [32] Z. Zhou, Y. Lin, H. Tang and H.A. Sodano, Hydrothermal growth of highly textured BaTiO₃ films composed of nanowires, *Nanotechnology*, **24**, 2013, pp. 095602.
- [33] E. Ciftci, M. Rahaman and M. Shumsky, Hydrothermal precipitation and characterization of nanocrystalline BaTiO₃ particles, *J. Mater. Sci.*, **36**, 2001, pp. 4875-4882 (doi: 10.1023/A:1011828018247).
- [34] R. Bacsa, P. Ravindranathan and J. Dougherty, Electrochemical, hydrothermal, and electrochemical-hydrothermal synthesis of barium titanate thin films on titanium substrates, *J.Mater.Res.*, **7**, 1992, pp. 423-428 (doi: 10.1557/JMR.1992.0423).
- [35] M. Yoshimura, S. Yoo, M. Hayashi and N. Ishizawa, Preparation of BaTiO₃ thin film by hydrothermal electrochemical method, *Jpn. J. Appl. Phys*, **28**, 1989, pp. L2007 (doi: 10.1143/JJAP.28.L2007).